

Stochastic Best Improvement with Progressive Halving Hyperparameter Optimization for Image Classification

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Abstract—Hyperparameter Optimization (HPO) is essential for enhancing Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) performance, yet often computationally demanding. This paper explores a lightweight HPO approach that combines Stochastic Best Improvement (SBI), a local search strategy sampling from a parameter neighborhood, with Progressive Halving, a resource-aware evaluation method commonly used in Hyperband. To balance performance and efficiency, we integrate transfer learning by structuring the CNN as sequential blocks—retaining pretrained weights in early blocks and applying HPO selectively to later ones. Using MobileNetV3 Small as a seed model, our proof-of-concept demonstrates minor accuracy improvements within limited search iterations. Notably, an emergent trend of reduced model size was observed when bounding neighborhood configurations by parameter count, leading to more efficient models with comparable or slightly improved accuracy. These findings suggest a practical pathway toward efficient, flexible CNN optimization under constrained resources.

Index Terms—Hyperparameter Optimization, Local Search, Convolutional Neural Networks, Image Classification, MobileNet

I. INTRODUCTION

Hyperparameter Optimization (HPO) remains a critical yet computationally intensive component in the development of high-performing Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) for image classification tasks. While automated search strategies have shown promise in identifying optimal hyperparameter configurations, their computational cost often renders them impractical, particularly when applied to deep models or in resource-constrained environments. This challenge is further complicated by the increasing reliance on transfer learning, where pretrained models are fine-tuned for downstream tasks. In such cases, the question arises: how can we efficiently conduct HPO while leveraging the benefits of pretrained weights and avoiding the full cost of training?

This work addresses this challenge by proposing a lightweight, modular HPO strategy that integrates two key components. First, we employ Stochastic Best Improvement, a local search technique that samples from a neighborhood of candidate configurations and selects the best-performing one. This method is coupled with Progressive Halving, a resource-aware evaluation mechanism that incrementally allocates training epochs to promising candidates while pruning underperforming ones. Second, we incorporate transfer learning at a structural level, treating CNN architectures as a sequence of modular blocks. Early blocks are initialized with pretrained weights and kept frozen, while HPO is applied flexibly to the remaining unfrozen blocks. This block-wise approach enables a trade-off between leveraging prior knowledge and exploring new configurations.

To further manage computational load, we introduce a constrained neighborhood sampling strategy that bounds candidate architectures by parameter count. Originally designed to avoid memory overflows during training, this constraint unexpectedly led to an emergent pattern: the search process tended to favor smaller, more efficient models that maintained or slightly improved classification accuracy. Using MobileNetV3 Small as the seed architecture, we demonstrate this approach in a proof-of-concept study. Although limited to a small number of search iterations due to computational constraints, our method achieved modest improvements in accuracy and yielded more compact models—offering a promising direction for practical, resource-aware HPO.

Our contributions are summarized as follows:

- We propose a hybrid HPO method combining Stochastic Best Improvement with Progressive Halving for efficient evaluation under budget constraints.

- We introduce a block-wise transfer learning strategy, enabling selective optimization of CNN substructures.
- We apply a parameter-bounded search neighborhood, leading to emergent model compression without explicit compression techniques.
- We validate the feasibility of the approach using MobileNetV3 Small on image classification task, showing minor but consistent improvements in accuracy and efficiency.

II. RELATED WORK

Hyperparameter optimization (HPO) plays a critical role in enhancing Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) performance, particularly for image classification tasks. Numerous studies have explored both classical and nature-inspired methods to optimize CNN architectures and training parameters.

Bayesian optimization has been extensively used to tune key hyperparameters such as learning rate, dropout, and optimizer settings, demonstrating strong performance across different CNN variants [1] [2]. In particular, Loey et al. [1] applied Bayesian optimization to a modified AlexNet for COVID-19 detection from chest X-ray images, achieving notable improvements in classification accuracy. Albelwi and Mahmood [2] applied the same technique to a deep CNN for general image recognition, emphasizing automatic model tuning. The Tree-structured Parzen Estimator (TPE) was also investigated in neural network settings for geospatial image classification, where Rong et al. [3] optimized a shallow CNN for geospatial pixel-wise classification of landslide risk.

Evolutionary algorithms have gained attention due to their flexibility and robustness in exploring high-dimensional search spaces. Genetic Algorithms (GA) have been used to optimize both the architecture and training parameters of CNNs, such as in Lee et al. [4], where the authors applied GA to a CNN trained on the Alzheimer’s PET/CT dataset for image classification, achieving improved generalization through evolved activation functions and layer configurations. Differential Evolution (DE) was used by Vili [5] to optimize a fine-tuned VGG19-based CNN for sports image classification, where DE focused on tuning network topology and training hyperparameters in transfer learning. Singh et al. [6] employed Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) to optimize feature selection in a CNN-based facial emotion recognition system, particularly tuning PSO-embedded parameters to improve emotion classification accuracy.

Several nature-inspired metaheuristics have also been applied effectively. Raiaan et al. [7] used the Grey Wolf Optimizer (GWO) to tune CNN parameters such as input preprocessing and network depth for fruit image classification. Bacanin et al. [8] applied the Firefly Algorithm (FA) to optimize CNN weight initialization and convergence in glioma brain tumor classification from MRI scans, showing faster training and higher accuracy. Simulated Annealing (SA) was used by Gülcü Kuş [9] in a multi-objective setting to balance classification accuracy and inference time on a CNN trained for plant disease detection.

Recent works also highlight the importance of multi-objective HPO (MOHPO), considering trade-offs between accuracy and computational cost (e.g., FLOPs), as shown by Gülcü Kuş (2021) [9]. Other strategies such as multi-level and hierarchical optimization divide the process into rough and fine-tuning stages for better control over search granularity [10] [11]. Yaloveha et al. [10] proposed a two-level tuning method applied to CNNs for aerial image classification, while Chen et al. [11] demonstrated hierarchical tuning of residual networks for medical image analysis.

To address the high computational cost of CNN training, early-stopping and resource-aware methods like Hyperband [12] have been proposed. These approaches reduce unnecessary evaluations by allocating resources adaptively and discarding underperforming configurations early in the process. Similarly, image downsampling as a preprocessing step was used by Hinz et al. [13] to accelerate CNN training in remote sensing applications while maintaining relative performance trends.

These advancements underline the ongoing need for efficient, scalable HPO strategies tailored to CNNs, especially in high-dimensional or resource-constrained scenarios.

III. APPROACH

A. Problem Formulation

Let $\mathcal{D}_{\text{train}}$ and \mathcal{D}_{val} represent the training and validation datasets, respectively. Consider a CNN model architecture \mathcal{A} composed of modular blocks, and let \mathcal{H} denote the space of hyperparameter configurations. The objective of Hyperparameter Optimization (HPO) in this context is to find the configuration $h^* \in \mathcal{H}$ that maximizes validation accuracy:

$$h^* = \arg \max_{h \in \mathcal{H}} \mathcal{A}_{\text{val}}(f(\mathcal{D}_{\text{train}}, h)), \quad (1)$$

where $f(\cdot, h)$ denotes the model trained using hyperparameter configuration h , and \mathcal{A}_{val} is the accuracy metric evaluated on the validation set.

To incorporate transfer learning, we partition the model architecture \mathcal{A} into two disjoint subsets of layers or blocks:

- $\mathcal{A}_{\text{frozen}}$: early blocks initialized with pretrained weights w_{pre} , kept fixed during training.
- $\mathcal{A}_{\text{tunable}}$: later blocks subject to weight training and HPO.

The composed model can then be expressed as:

$$f(\mathcal{D}_{\text{train}}, h) = \mathcal{A}_{\text{frozen}}(w_{\text{pre}}) \circ \mathcal{A}_{\text{tunable}}(w(h)), \quad (2)$$

where $w(h)$ are the learned weights resulting from training the tunable portion under configuration h , and \circ denotes functional composition.

The final optimization problem becomes:

$$h^* = \arg \max_{h \in \mathcal{H}} \mathcal{A}_{\text{val}}(\mathcal{A}_{\text{frozen}}(w_{\text{pre}}) \circ \mathcal{A}_{\text{tunable}}(w(h))), \quad (3)$$

subject to practical constraints such as training budget. This formulation captures a balance between leveraging stable, high-quality pretrained features and maintaining flexibility in optimizing the remaining parts of the model via HPO.

B. Model Seeding

Our methodology is centered on the hyperparameter optimization (HPO) of a MobileNetV3 based architecture [14]. The network is deconstructed into fundamental, modular Blocks, which serve as the primary components for modification and tuning. These blocks primarily consist of Inverted Residuals, which feature an efficient expand depthwise project structure, and may optionally include Squeeze and Excitation (SE) modules for dynamic channel wise feature recalibration [15]. The core hyperparameters defining these blocks such as channel counts, kernel sizes, and activation functions form the search space for our optimization.

For our initial experiments, we employed a strategy inspired by transfer learning principles. The first eight blocks of the network were frozen, preserving their learned weights from the pre-trained model. This decision is based on the premise that earlier layers in a CNN capture fundamental, low level features (e.g., edges, textures) that are broadly generalizable. Consequently, our HPO efforts were exclusively focused on the terminal five blocks and the final classifier layer. These deeper blocks are responsible for abstracting more complex, task specific features, and their optimization is therefore more critical for adapting the model to the target dataset.

A significant outcome of this HPO methodology is the inherent generation of models that are computationally lighter than the original MobileNetV3 baseline. This is because the hyperparameter search space is designed to explore architectural variations that can be more efficient. The optimization algorithm, systematically explores configurations with reduced channel dimensions, smaller kernel sizes, or even the selective removal of components like the SE module within the unfrozen blocks. Unlike the fixed, monolithic structure of the baseline, our search process actively seeks a Pareto optimal frontier between accuracy and computational cost. Therefore, any resulting architecture is, by design, a tailored and often simplified variant of the original, leading to a reduction in model size and inference latency.

Fig. 1: Architecture of MobileNetV3. The model utilizes depthwise separable convolutions for efficient feature extraction, followed by inverted residual bottleneck blocks. Key architectural components include Squeeze-and-Excitation (SE) modules for channel-wise attention, and BatchNorm-Activation (BNAct) blocks. A global adaptive average pooling layer and a final 1×1 point wise convolution complete the network.

Fig. 2: Block-level transfer learning strategy applied to the MobileNetV3 architecture. The first K blocks are frozen with pre-trained ImageNet weights, while the last $N - K$ blocks are optimized using hyperparameter search.

C. Hyperparameters & Neighborhood

1) *Hyperparameters*: Executing a hyperparameter optimization (HPO) algorithm requires the specification of a set of tunable hyperparameters. Any hyperparameter not included in this set is fixed to a predetermined value. The table below outlines the elements of this tunable set, along with the corresponding search space defined for each variable. To maintain clarity, we employ the following abbreviations: **CB** refers to Convolution Block, **SE** denotes Squeeze Excitation, and **IR** stands for Inverted Residual.

TABLE I: hyperparameter configurations.

Hyperparameter	Affected Part	Search Space
Stride	CB	{1, 2}
Kernel size	CB	{3, 5, 7}
Channels number	CB	{8, 16, 24..., 160}
Activation function	CB & Classifier	{Relu, Hardswish}
Activation function	SE	{Hardsigmoid, sigmoid}
Squeeze factor	SE	{4, 8, 16}
Expanding channels number	IR	{8, 16, 24..., 320}
Dropout rate	Classifier	{0.1, 0.2, 0.3}
Number of neurons	Classifier	{64, 128, 192..., 1024}

2) *Neighborhood Strategy*: The development of a local search-based HPO algorithm entails the definition of a neighborhood structure for a given architecture configuration. In this work, we adopt an instantiation-based approach, in which the neighborhood is not explicitly enumerated. Instead, neighboring configurations are sampled in accordance with the pseudo-algorithm presented below [9].

Algorithm 1 Neighboring Architecture sampling pseudo-algorithm

Input: Model architecture, block modification ratio (**bmr** in %), parameter modification ratio (**pmr** in %), modification_strategy, perturbation intensity (**pi**)

Output: Modified architecture

```

1 foreach block in architecture do
2   if block is not frozen then
3     if random() ≤ bmr then
4       // The block's content will be
         modified
5       foreach tunable hyperparameter in block do
6         if random() ≤ pmr then
7           // The HP value will be
             modified
8           if modification_strategy is local then
9             | new value = sample_locally(pi)
10            else if modification_strategy is random
              then
                | new value = sample_randomly()
              Assign value to hyperparameter

```

The core mechanism of the algorithm consists of the probabilistic modification of hyperparameter values within each block, guided by a predefined strategy. We propose two such strategies. The first, referred to as the local strategy, selects a new value from the hyperparameter’s search space that either precedes or follows the current value by a fixed index offset (perturbation intensity), resulting in a more controlled perturbation. The second, termed the random strategy, selects a new value uniformly at random from the hyperparameter’s search space, thereby introducing a less controlled perturbation.

Fig. 3: Comparison between the random and local hyperparameter update strategies

D. Local Search & Evaluation

Fine-tuning large-scale, state-of-the-art models poses significant computational challenges due to both extended training durations and expansive hyperparameter search spaces. Exhaustively evaluating all candidate configurations becomes computationally prohibitive, especially under resource constraints. To address these challenges, we propose a local

search framework termed *Stochastic Best Improvement with Progressive Halving*.

This method combines two key strategies:

- **Progressive Halving** [12]: Rather than allocating the full training budget to all candidate models, we iteratively eliminate poorly performing configurations early and re-allocate computational resources to more promising ones. This allows faster convergence with fewer resources.
- **Stochastic Neighborhood Sampling**: Instead of evaluating the full neighborhood of the current model configuration, we randomly sample a fixed number of neighbors according to a predefined strategy. This enables efficient exploration of the search space without exhaustive enumeration.

At each iteration, a set of n neighboring configurations is sampled. Each candidate is initially trained for a small number of epochs. The worst-performing half of the candidates is discarded, and the remaining ones are trained further with an increased epoch budget. This halving process continues until either one candidate remains or the maximum number of epochs is reached. The best-performing configuration is selected and compared against the current model; if it yields an improvement, the search continues from this new point. Otherwise, the algorithm terminates.

The detailed procedure is presented in Algorithm 2.

Algorithm 2 Stochastic Best Improvement with Progressive Halving

Require: Initial configuration m_0 , neighborhood size n , maximum number of epochs max_epochs

Ensure: Best configuration m^*

```

1:  $m \leftarrow m_0$ 
2: while termination criterion not met do
3:   Sample a neighborhood  $\mathcal{N} = \{m_1, m_2, \dots, m_n\}$ 
         around  $m$ 
4:   Set initial epoch budget  $e \leftarrow \frac{max\_epochs}{2^{\lfloor \log_2(n) \rfloor}}$ 
5:   Initialize candidate set  $\mathcal{C} \leftarrow \mathcal{N}$ 
6:   while  $|\mathcal{C}| > 1$  and  $e \leq max\_epochs$  do
7:     for each model  $m_i \in \mathcal{C}$  do
8:       Train  $m_i$  for  $e$  epochs
9:       Evaluate and record validation performance of  $m_i$ 
10:    end for
11:    Sort  $\mathcal{C}$  by performance
12:    Retain top  $\lfloor |\mathcal{C}|/2 \rfloor$  models in  $\mathcal{C}$ 
13:     $e \leftarrow 2e$ 
14:  end while
15:   $m' \leftarrow$  best model in  $\mathcal{C}$ 
16:  if performance( $m'$ ) > performance( $m$ ) then
17:     $m \leftarrow m'$ 
18:  else
19:    break
20:  end if
21: end while
22: return  $m$ 

```

Figure 4 provides a visual illustration of the proposed method.

Fig. 4: Stochastic Best Improvement with Progressive Halving

This approach strikes a balance between exploration and efficiency, enabling effective hyperparameter optimization in scenarios with limited computational resources.

IV. EXPERIMENTS & RESULTS

This section presents the experimental setup, evaluation methodology, and key findings. All experiments were conducted using an NVIDIA GTX 1650 4GB Mobile GPU. Our goal is to evaluate the performance of state-of-the-art (SOTA) models on the CIFAR-10 dataset [17], study the effect of pretraining, investigate progressive freezing strategies, and analyze the outcomes of hyperparameter optimization (HPO).

A. SOTA Models Evaluations

We evaluated several SOTA convolutional neural networks (CNNs) on CIFAR-10 [17], training each model for a single epoch, with and without pretraining.

TABLE II: SOTA Models Without Pretraining on CIFAR-10 (1 Epoch)

Model	Train Loss	Train Acc (%)	Test Loss	Test Acc (%)	Time (min)
ResNet18	1.3295	52.44	1.3399	55.62	4.16
EfficientNet-B0	1.4382	49.07	1.0285	63.32	5.74
MobileNetV3	1.4267	48.76	1.3144	57.85	2.60
DenseNet121	1.3741	50.71	1.1887	56.05	10.57
RegNetY-400MF	1.4682	46.97	1.2201	56.47	4.56
SqueezeNet	1.8678	30.12	1.5843	41.43	4.08
VGG11	2.4707	19.25	1.8457	30.76	9.49

1) *Evaluation without Pretraining:* EfficientNet-B0 achieved the best test accuracy (63.32%) even without pretraining. MobileNetV3 had the fastest training time (2.6 minutes), making it suitable for rapid experimentation.

TABLE III: SOTA Models With Pretraining on CIFAR-10 (1 Epoch)

Model	Train Loss	Train Acc (%)	Test Loss	Test Acc (%)	Time (min)
ResNet18	0.6291	79.79	0.5170	82.16	4.16
EfficientNet-B0	0.4239	86.95	0.2251	92.38	5.77
MobileNetV3	0.4754	84.90	0.3338	88.53	2.56
DenseNet121	0.5591	82.00	0.4351	85.69	10.56
RegNetY-400MF	0.4462	86.10	0.2969	89.88	4.56
SqueezeNet	1.6482	40.49	1.2044	55.55	4.08
VGG11	1.3774	50.02	1.4773	56.56	9.46

2) *Evaluation with Pretraining:* Pretraining significantly boosted performance across all models. EfficientNet-B0 again achieved the highest test accuracy (92.38%).

B. Impact of Progressive Freezing

We progressively froze the blocks of the backbone during training. Accuracy increased up to 11 blocks before saturating.

TABLE IV: Model Accuracy vs. Number of Frozen Blocks

Frozen Blocks	Train Acc (%)	Test Acc (%)
0	91.17	80.41
5	93.91	83.02
9	97.03	86.50
11	97.47	90.09
13	98.01	89.38

Progressive Halving Evaluation: We used progressive halving to explore neighbor architectures. Accuracy improvements are reported below:

TABLE V: Progressive Halving Evaluation

Iter.	First Acc	Best Acc	Δ Acc	% Gain
1	80.31	80.31	0.00	0.00
4	79.60	81.20	1.60	2.01
8	79.56	80.86	1.30	1.63

C. Optimization Results

Initial HPO Run: We performed a Stochastic Best Improvement search over 10 iterations, increasing best accuracy from 82.45% to 82.90%.

TABLE VI: Key Architectural Changes – Initial HPO Run

Component	Change
Upsample factor	6 \rightarrow 8
Last conv channels	576 \rightarrow 768
Classifier neurons	1024 \rightarrow 768
Dropout	0.2 \rightarrow 0.1
Block 7	exp_channels: 120 \rightarrow 104 channels: 48 \rightarrow 40 kernel size: 5 \rightarrow 7 activation: Hardswish \rightarrow ReLU squeeze: 4 \rightarrow 8
Block 9	exp_channels: 288 \rightarrow 296 channels: 96 \rightarrow 88 kernel size: 5 \rightarrow 7
Block 10	activation: Hardswish \rightarrow ReLU squeeze: 4 \rightarrow 8
Block 11	exp_channels: 576 \rightarrow 312 kernel: 5 \rightarrow 7, stride: 1 \rightarrow 2 activation: Hardswish \rightarrow ReLU

Second HPO Run (VM): This run reduced model parameters from 1.528M to 1.019M while achieving a best accuracy of 86.80%.

Third HPO Run: The third run focused on efficiency and reduced parameters further to 0.574M, while slightly improving accuracy from 86.47% to 86.48%.

TABLE VII: Final Modifications – Third HPO Run

Component	Change
Block 8	exp_channels: 120 → 104 channels: 48 → 40 kernel size: 5 → 7 activation: Hardswish → ReLU squeeze: 4 → 8
Block 11	exp_channels: 576 → 312 kernel: 5 → 7, stride: 1 → 2
Last conv upsample	6 → 1
Last conv channels	576 → 120
Classifier activation	Hardswish → ReLU
Classifier dropout	0.2 → 0.0

TABLE VIII: Summary of HPO Runs – Accuracy and Parameter Reduction

Run	Accuracy	Δ Acc	Rel. Gain	Params	Reduction
Initial	82.90%	+0.45%	—	1.528M	—
Second	86.80%	+3.90%	+4.71%	1.019M	-509K (33.3%)
Third	86.48%	-0.32%	-0.37%	0.574M	-445K (43.7%)

V. CONCLUSION

In this work, we presented a resource-conscious framework for Hyperparameter Optimization (HPO) in Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), combining Stochastic Best Improvement with Progressive Halving to efficiently explore the hyperparameter space. To further improve practicality, we introduced a block-wise transfer learning strategy that retains pretrained weights in early network blocks while applying HPO flexibly to later layers. This modular approach enables an effective trade-off between leveraging pretrained knowledge and preserving optimization flexibility.

Our proof-of-concept experiments using MobileNetV3 Small demonstrated that even with a limited number of search iterations, modest accuracy improvements (1–2%) can be achieved. More notably, by constraining the search neighborhood based on parameter count—a decision originally motivated by engineering constraints—we observed an emergent trend toward smaller, more efficient models that maintained or slightly improved performance.

These findings suggest a practical pathway for CNN optimization under real-world constraints, such as limited computational resources or deployment on memory-constrained devices. Future work will explore scaling the method to larger datasets and architectures, incorporating more sophisticated neighborhood sampling techniques, and formalizing the emergent behavior observed in model compression.

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